

CARETUNES: TURNING PATIENT VITALS INTO MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents CareTunes as a concept to explore musical sonification of patient vitals and the role of music in Intensive Care Units (ICU). In this paper, we first describe the design specifications for the sonification of data in a musical fashion. Secondly, we present two applications for CareTunes in prototype stage and user evaluation studies. The first application regards the ICU nurses' need to monitor patients from a distance (CareTunes as musical updates for nurses) and second application regards families' need to connect with their loved in the ICU (CareTunes as musical messages for families). We conclude that music has the potential to represent changes in patient vitals for nurses and emotionally regulate families' anxieties regarding ICU patient's condition. Music offers a platform for reutilizing patient data for human-centered solutions.

1. INTRODUCTION

CareTunes is a concept that challenges the clinical utilization of data from patient monitoring devices found in Intensive Care Units (ICU). **CareTunes** is developed to explore methods for continuous musical stream that summarizes patient vital signs and presents them in a coherent, logical, and pleasant way to the clinicians (mainly the nurse) and families. In this paper, we first describe the technical requirements for CareTunes and its design specifications for the sonification of data. Secondly, we present two applications for CareTunes in prototype stage and user evaluation studies. The first application regards the ICU nurses' need to monitor patients from a distance (CareTunes as musical updates for nurses) and second application regards families' need to connect with their loved in the ICU (CareTunes as musical messages for families). Overall, this paper demonstrates our vision and pose critique on sound design in healthcare by discussing the role of music in ICUs and novel ways of using healthcare data.

Our motivation to explore music also comes from the need to eliminate cacophony and introduce harmony in the soundscapes of complex work spaces and healing environments. Essentially, we are exploring ways of sonification and its manifestation in the form of music which can offer richer data representations and pave the road for customization of sonified data by providing a systemic approach for data representation with its own rules. Music is also a

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familiar concept among people as daily musical interactions allow potential users to gain a perceptual repertoire and quickly interpret notation or infer abstract meaning.

1.1 Intensive Care Units

People are admitted to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) when they are in a life-threatening situation, and special equipment is used to constantly monitor, support, and/or take over their bodily functions. ICU patients often require much rest, and some may be sedated, such as patients on mechanical ventilators. The average ICU length of stay is around 3.3 days [1]. However, it is influenced by several factors, such as the type of disease or surgery. For example, the average length of stay of COVID-19 patients is estimated to be around seven to eight days at the time the research was conducted [2]. The COVID-19 situation calls attention to people who are hospitalised for a longer period in the ICU. Families of ICU patients often experience distress and anxiety. They have emotional and social needs such as assurance and closeness, but oftentimes they cannot make contact with the patient, due to the medical restrictions or because the patient is unconscious. Such difficulties are emphasized during the COVID-19 pandemic, as patients may be transported to hospitals far from home due to the limited capacity of ICUs. This points to a demand for a stronger patient-family connection and connectedness. Nurses working in the ICU are exposed to a vast amount of sounds from medical equipment. The amount of alarms nurses cope with causes alarms fatigue, which causes nurses to become desensitised to alarms. Not only is this a threat to patient safety, it also causes stress.

1.2 The need for music in the ICU

Music can serve as a design approach for healthcare [3] as it is a powerful way to communicate emotions and meanings and it also exerts physical and behavioral effects [4]. With the power to express meaning, it is possible to use music to pass on information about the patient to the clinicians or family. Music can also be used to enhance or reduce positive or negative emotions, or simply to regulate levels of arousal [5]. Therefore, music has the quality to fulfill the social needs, emotional needs, and need for information at the same time. Furthermore, some events may have a more natural representation in sound [6]. Bly stated that: "Because perception of sound is different than visual perception, sound can offer a different intuitive view of the information it presents." [7] While numbers, texts, and the image of a loved one being unconscious may feel unfamiliar to their families, music may allow people to connect with the patient in a more natural way.

1.3 Communicating Information with Music

Research into music communication and Sonic Interaction Design (SID) offers guidance for designing music to communicate information [6] [8] [9]. For example, sound is better suited to display relative data than absolute data with high precision [6]. Therefore, if music is used to display everchanging information, such as the physiological data of the patient, it is not necessary, nor aesthetically pleasing, for the music to change precisely with every detail of the data it translates. Musical communication is not only about the music providing information, but also about people interpreting the music. Factors that may affect musical communication include musical features, situations and contexts, and individual preferences and knowledge [10]. Therefore, the meaning of the music may not be fixed, but rather changeable as fluids within certain boundaries, in relation to the listener's experience [11]. The mental space for imagination and interpretation can have its advantages and disadvantages. For example, it can make the listening experience more intimate as it allows the listener to give meanings to the music based on perception of the context in an emotional way. Nevertheless, the listener's individual preferences or emotions can greatly influence their interpretation of the music's meaning, making it difficult to design accurately for an intended effect using music. We conclude that the strength of music communication lies in its ability to facilitate the listener to perceive information in a humanized way with emotions considered.

1.4 Influencing emotions through music

Justin and Västfjäll [12] concluded six mechanisms through which music listening may induce emotions: *i.* brain stem reflexes (e.g., arousal feelings when hearing sudden, loud, dissonant sounds), *ii.* evaluative conditioning (memory of music stimulus paired with other positive or negative stimuli), *iii.* emotional contagion, *iv.* visual imagery, *v.* episodic memory (relating music with a past event), and *vi.* musical expectancy (e.g., surprise caused by changes). Instead, the transitions in music are designed to be gradual. Examples in using music to cause emotional contagion include the use of different timbres. For instance, the timbre of string instruments has a higher emotional quality due to its voice-like characteristic [5]. While the strings are able to evoke more longing, sadness and tenderness, piano can evoke more joy [13]. Furthermore, music may reduce anxiety by making people attuned to its melodies and harmonies. Lee et al. [14] concluded that the characteristics of anxiety-reducing music include *simple repetitive rhythms, predictable dynamics, low pitch, slow tempos, the consonance of harmony, a lack of percussive instrumentals and vocal timbres*. However, there has been no consistent agreement on the type of music, and people's musical preferences remain one of the most important factors in the effect of the use of music as a design tool [14].

1.5 Timbre and tempo as design principles

Patient data are continuous by nature and fluctuate upon metabolic events. In a sonification of patient data, key, tempo, pitch and timbre could all be used to represent values of the different parameters involved. It is the sudden

or drastic changes in the values that are monitored and acted upon. An important criterion for the design is whether or not listeners will likely be able to detect changes in sonification by foreground and background effects. Timbre seems to be an aspect of sound that is quite universally recognised by people. People are able to remember the voice of someone they know and recognise it. Differences between musical instruments, especially from different families, can be heard by most untrained people. A guitar clearly sounds different than a trumpet, even when playing the same note. In 'Remembering the melody and timbre, forgetting the key and tempo', Schellenbach and Habaschi [15] show how people perform better at the memorisation of melodies when the timbre remains the same in both instances they heard it in. This implies timbre plays a role in recognition of melodies. Wolpert [16] even shows that to people without musical training, timbre has a bigger influence on the perception of a musical excerpt than harmonics; when non-musicians were asked to select the excerpt they heard earlier, 95% selected a sample in which the instrumentation is unchanged, ignoring that sample's incorrect harmonic accompaniment. If non-musicians are indeed inclined to recognise musical samples by their timbre, this would be a useful attribute for to represent data in a sonification. It would mean users could listen to the sonification and recognise changes in the values sonification represents without having to identify tonal or harmonic changes. This can make the design less reliable on musical training.

Levitin and Cook [17] show that the memory of a piece of music contains a reasonably accurate tempo for that piece; when people were asked to reproduce a song they had not heard for at least 72 hours, the majority of people were able to reproduce the tempo of the song with an error of only 8% or less. This suggests there is an absolute memory of tempo when people remember a song. A musical sonification will inherently have a certain tempo. Because people have a reasonably accurate memory of a tempo of a musical piece they have heard before, this tempo, like timbre, seems a suitable aspect of music for the representation of data.

2. PROTOTYPING CARETUNES

2.1 Sonifying patient vitals

A first prototype is built to demonstrate the concept of using three of a patient's vital signs to influence the way different parts of music sound. We examined 48 hours of anonymized patient data from Drager Patient Monitors to characterize patient data flow. The data offer changes in patient vitals, which then input different software synthesizers. The musical prototype that is presented as a result the first cycle consists of a Max MSP program (Figure 1) that sonifies three patient vitals that are often monitored on the patient monitor: heart rate (HR), Oxygen levels in the blood (SpO2), and blood pressure (BP). Manipulating synthesizers based on data can be done with the help of Max MSP. Max also offers integration with Ableton Live, which will become instrumental in prototyping later design

Figure 1. The state diagram for the Max patch.

iterations. In this first design attempt, software synthesisers and audio effects that are integrated in Max are used to generate musical motives. Parameters of the software synthesisers that influence its timbre can be manipulated based on the numbers of simulated patient vitals. Figure 1 shows a state diagram of how the Max patch works.

2.2 Musical complexities.

A second prototype was built to demonstrate the concept of switching between different complexities in the musical composition and also to explore the role of individual musical taste. Therefore, Ableton Live is selected as the most suitable tool for this prototype. Ableton Live is a program for music sequencing and arranging (Ableton.com). Ableton Live is preferred mostly because of its integration with Max, which makes it possible to automate parameters in audio effects from Max. In the ‘session view’ in Live, one can record audio or midi ‘tracks’ that all contain ‘clips’. These clips can be triggered, either in the interface itself or from external hardware, allowing the user to create a composition out of pre-recorded samples or midi sequences. Three simple compositions, changing in genre (i.e., pop, jazz, ambient), are written in Ableton Live all consisting of a chord progression accompanied by drums and a bass line. Within a composition, there are four different versions of each composition, each of which is slightly more complex than the previous one. This is achieved by adding extra bass notes, adding accents in the drum part or by playing the notes of the chord sequentially and more often. Musical scores for the two out of four intensities of one of the ‘genres’ are shown in Figure 2.

2.2.1 Evaluation of the concept.

Our aim was to understand whether the participants would be able to recognise the changes in timbre and whether they would need to change between songs and musical complexities for a long-term listening (effect of tempo). Genres were used to address individual music preferences.

Figure 2. Broken chord and more elaborate drum and bass rhythms make the piece sound more complex.

Participants. Seven design students (4 males and 3 females) participated in the evaluation with a mean age of 23,5 years.

Set-up and procedure. The prototype that simulates the current version of the CareTunes concept played from Ableton Live on a laptop. The participant would listen to the continuous song (i.e., musical sonification) from this laptop while working. The participant was able to control the prototype through the Open Sound Control interface (OSC). The researcher triggered changes in timbre from the computer, which the participant could then react by pressing a button on OSC. Participants were given the task to recognise changes in timbre and indicate them on the mobile device. If they would prefer a more exciting version of the song they chose which would increase its ‘complexity’ on the OSC. Participants were also asked to indicate when they want to listen to a different sonification on the mobile device via OSC, and a new song started playing once they do so. Participants were occupied with another task while they listened to the songs for the duration of the test (i.e., one hour) to see whether the changes in the music could be detected when people are distracted.

A semi-structured interview was conducted after the test to get a grasp of how well participants are able to recognise different timbres and how confident they feel in doing so. The following questions were used in this interview. What is the participant’s overall impression of the sonification? How hard was it for the participant to recognise and distinguish the changes? How quickly did the sonification start to bore the participant? Were the sonifications distracting from the work participants were trying to do?

Measurements. Timestamped notes of the user’s behaviour are recorded including when they change the intensity or when they seem in doubt about how to respond to the soundscape, the number of times the user successfully and unsuccessfully recognises a change in timbre. The users verbally answer the interview questions.

Results. The results from the user test are divided into the measured results and the participants’ answers to interview questions. The amount of time that participants were able to listen to the songs before they wanted to switch to a next one is reflected by the measured results of their behaviour. Participant quotes from the interview show how they felt about the different songs and complexities and switching between them. Figure 3 shows the participant’s behaviour in switching between songs and what they thought about this. A large majority of timbre changes was successfully recognised by participants (Table 1). Participant quotes show how they experienced the task.

Figure 3. The moments participants changed songs (see the ‘play’ icon) during 60 minutes and their specific comments. The thickness of the lines changes as participants seek for a more complex musical structure.

Song-like sonifications can make it hard to consistently recognise changes. As one listens to a song, it is quite normal to hear changes in timbre as a part of it. Instruments may be played in different ways, or sound effects may be applied by the artist. The song-like structure in the current design therefore confuses people in whether the changes they hear are a part of the song or if they hear something they are supposed to point out.

Switching between songs can make it more interesting to listen to the soundscape for a long time, but can also make it harder to get used to using the sonification. Participants in the test were able to switch between different soundscapes and they did so roughly every ten minutes. The amount of time one can comfortably listen to the sonification can be increased by adding more songs. Some participants did however notice that they they had to

get used to the new song to easily recognise timbre changes again.

Songs have parts that are layered, sounding at the same time, making it harder to distinguish them. Using a song like structure in the sonifications means each part representing a datapoint may sound at the same time as another part. Some of the participants were very easily able to detect a change in the song overall, but found it difficult to point out which of the part it was.

There is a learning curve to using CareTunes. Most participants note that it becomes easier to work with the sonification as they are listening to them for a while. This indicates working with a song may require a certain amount of training by the nurse.

	Hit/miss	Participant quotes
Drums	20/23	"One of the changes was a bit more subtle than the others. The drums were really clear." "That change was not really disturbing. I thought it was just a different [effect] pedal or something."
Bass	22/23	"At first the changes were hard to recognise, but I got used to it and it became easier." "Changing the intensity just makes me doubt if I heard a change or not."
Piano	16/25	"Doesn't sound very alarming"

Table 1. Participants’ success rate in recognizing changes in timbre.

3. CARETUNES – MUSICAL UPDATES

Medical alarms are quite often misused as nurses look for possibilities to be constantly aware of the situation. The basic premise of an alarm use is to be notified when action needs to be taken [18]. Alarms seem to be often used by nurses as a constant status report. Nurses can do this by setting limits more tightly than they need to be, to be notified when the parameter approaches the actual limit. This use of alarms is the cause of many non-actionable alarms. Because of this, nurses can get used to switching off alarms right after they occur without attending to the patient. Currently, alarms used for monitoring patients do not carry the kind of information nurses may practically need [19]. Nurses need knowledge about several values measured by equipment to judge how they need to respond. Current alarms never give them this information except for the very worst cases, like an asystole alarm, is it immediately clear what action needs to be taken. All the less severe alarms (i.e., yellow alarms) may mean that any of the patient’s vital signs slightly exceeds the value that has been set as a limit. It does not convey which vital sign has exceeded the limit, by how far it has done so, or even whether it surpassed the low or the high limit. This means nurses nearly always need to verify the state of the patient by checking the exact values, often to find out no action needs to be taken.

3.1 Design considerations for musical updates

The song-like structure of the sonification in the previous cycle made it hard for users to distinguish between the different parameters they were listening to. A brainstorm session with three trained musicians was organised to fulfill nurses’ needs in relation to the sonification design. Several

requirements for the sonification were used as a starting point for the session: *i.* Each instrument used in the sonification to represent a different parameter should be easily distinguishable; *ii.* Four levels of timbre change on each side of the safe middle should be recognisable by the listener. These should have clearly audible differences between values higher and lower than the middle value; *iii.* The timbre of each parameter should become less pleasant to listen to as it approaches the limit set for that parameter; *iv.* Sounds which represent a value over the limit should universally be regarded unpleasant to listen to; *v.* Instead of continuous music, the sonification should give the listener periodic updates.

Timbre change. For each parameter, the range between the upper and lower limit is divided into four segments above the safe middle and four segments below it. Each of these segments has its own timbre so the listener can identify each segment by listening. This allows the nurse to be aware of how much change occurs in one direction or the other. As the parameter approaches a low limit, the sound that represents that parameter will sound more muffled in each segment. This is achieved through the use of a low pass filter over the original, safe value sound. Each of the segments the frequency of the filter is changed just enough to create a noticeable difference from the segment that precedes it. The same technique is used to make each segment approaching an upper limit sound slightly sharper. In this case a high pass filter is used to achieve this effect.

Dissonance. The timbre changes indicate a parameter that reaches an unsafe value and help the nurse be more proactive in taking action as a patient’s vitals change. When a limit that a nurse has set is crossed by a parameter however, this should still be made very clear to the nurse, as a dangerous situation may be the result of this. To ensure the nurse’s attention is gained in such a situation, dissonance is used in the sonification. Dissonance in musical theory are notes that sound unstable together and need resolution. Out of key notes are added to the sound that represent the parameter that exceeds the limit. Out of rhythm sounds are added when this concerns the heart rate parameter. To look for the right solutions for these requirements, the session involved ideations with the help of Ableton Live and several MIDI instruments. A range of instruments and sound effects were tested to find those that could be used to create the desired amount different timbres. The result of the session was an overview of how changes in each of three vital functions will influence an audio effect. The parameters that are sonified were divided not just across different instruments, but across three different aspects of music: rhythm, harmony and melody. The three parts play in sequence to make them easier to distinguish. The listener hears three medical parameters, one by one (See Figure 4).

3.2 Usability test with nurses

A usability test with nurses was conducted to get more in-depth insights in how well CareTunes works and how it is experienced by nurses. The questions addressed by the user test are: What values do nurses intuitively assign to

the different timbres in each parameter they hear in Care Tunes? How well are nurses able to recognise the different parameters and the changes within them? Do the visual cues in the user interface support nurses in understanding what they hear? How do nurses feel about using Care-Tunes in their work? What do they see as advantages and disadvantages? Would they trust themselves to hear changes in the sonification?

Figure 4. An out of limit value is indicated by dissonance.

Participants. Four ICU nurses (two male, two female) with the same roles but different levels of experiences participated.

Procedure. Before starting the test, the basic principles of the design were explained to nurses. A storyboard was used to help the participant understand the role that Care-Tunes would fulfill in the ICU. The test started by the participant listening to the sonification first without and then with the GUI. The participant listened through on-ear headphones which allowed for conversation to take place while listening. While the participants listened to the simulated patient data, they were asked explain what they heard and what it could mean. When all timbre changes have been covered, a participant was debriefed.

Results and Conclusions. Two boards are used to show the difference between listening without and with the GUI. Quotes are linked to the different timbres that the nurses heard during the session, showing how they intuitively perceive them, and how this changed when the GUI was introduced. This gives the following insights.

Some of the timbres in each parameter intuitively sound urgent to participants. For other parameters, some participants feel the timbre change may be too subtle. Most participants were able to recognise the timbre change corresponding with a value close to the limit. All participants recognised a value crossing the limit. The introduction of

visual support clearly made it easier for participants to follow the parameters and hear which part of the music belongs to each of them. When listening to the sonification with visual support, some participants indicate the sonification sounds less urgent than they would expect for the heartrate and oxygen saturation parameters. Three participants felt wearing an earpiece would be convenient way of listening to CareTunes and one expressed discomfort and concern about nurses wearing hearing aids.

4. CARETUNES – MUSICAL MESSAGES

The music design of CareTunes as musical messages for Families focuses on emotional contagion and visual imagery. Emotional contagion as a concept can help us think of way to reduce negative emotions and evoke positive emotions, and visual imagery helps to communicate information regarding the patient state. Sudden changes in the music can avoided to prevent causing surprises or sudden emotional arousal. The data sources are selected according to what kind of information would better increase the sense of connectedness, and what the families would be likely to interpret or imagine (See Figure 5). This information includes the patient’s emotions, state of consciousness, and activities. Therefore, heart rate, brain waves, and movements serve as data sources for the music variations. Heart rate and brain waves are data that are on a spectrum. For example, a normal resting heart rate for adults ranges from 60 to 100 beats per minute (though some ICU patients’ heart rate can be higher due to increased metabolic rate [20]), and brainwaves are defined by electroencephalography (EEG) frequency: alpha wave (8-13Hz), theta wave (3-7Hz), etc. [21] Therefore, they are divided into levels when being presented in the music.

A mixture of meanings. Although the patient data sources are separate, they usually affect one another, often in a complex manner, and cannot be distinctly separated to represent respective meanings. For example, when a person starts exercising, their heart rate and movements would increase. Nevertheless, an increase in heart rate does not necessarily mean a person is exercising; it can also signify emotional arousal such as stress or excitement, as heart rate. Heart rate and brain waves also change according to a person falling asleep or waking up.

Limitations and alternatives. While heart rate is always monitored, continuous EEG monitoring is yet uncommon and still being developed in the context of ICU [22]. Motion sensors are not a standard equipment in the ICU, either. Nevertheless, this project included these data sources as a design vision for the ideal situation. If it is to be implemented without EEG and motion monitoring devices, alternatives can be considered, such as using heart rate to present the state of consciousness and physical activities. However, this may not have the same effect as using brain waves, because families might relate thoughts and emotions more to the brain, and regard the heart to have a more “biological” meaning, according to the user evaluation. It is also possible to eliminate the presentation of physical

activities and focus on presenting psychological activities. Meanwhile, this also points to one of the advantages of having multiple tracks of music in the design: it allows different ICUs to customize the music according to their resources and expertise.

Design Principles. The data derived from the monitoring devices should not be constantly changing to avoid evoking the feeling of instability and hence uncertainty. Therefore, the data is updated at regular intervals (e.g., every five minutes). In addition, if any track is to be added or removed from the music, it needs to follow the bars of the music and wait for the right moment to come in.

Figure 5. Data mapping of the music generation.

4.1 User evaluation with families

Two rounds of design and qualitative user evaluation provided insights into how music can better present the patient to the family while reducing negative emotions and inducing positive emotions.

Procedure. In the user tests, the participants answered a short questionnaire after listening to each piece of music, then participated in a structured interview based on their answers to the questionnaire. In the first round of user evaluation, the participants listened to three pieces of music; in the second round, the participants listened to four variations of one piece of music, and were able to access the music within 48 hours.

Participants. In order to gain in-depth feedback, a total of eight participants were selected to join the qualitative user evaluation. The first user test consisted of six participants (three males and three females, mean age 27,5 years), three with experience of a relative being in the ICU. The second user test consisted of two participants whose close relatives have stayed in the ICU.

Data Collection and Analysis. The data collection of the research is through structured interviews. In the interviews, the participants first explained their answers to a self-report questionnaire about their emotions affected by the music. The questionnaires mainly serve to guide the participants to reflect on their emotions and experience. The participants then proceeded to talk about how they interpreted the music, and what they thought the music told

them about their loved one in the ICU. The interview results are arranged into codebooks with different themes and sub-themes to present the commonality of emotional effect by music on people.

Results and Conclusions. Tables 2 and 3 show the results of the user evaluation interviews. In the first round of user evaluation, participants expressed that they feel more connected to their loved ones when the music feels more positive and tender. Furthermore, the continuous stream of music felt like the continuous presence of the patient. Participants also pointed out that, when the music directly presents the crucial information, such as the heartbeat of the patient, they feel worried and uncertain. Meanwhile, the music feels more meaningful when they present the patient’s emotions and activities. In the second round of user evaluation, more patient data are included in the music composition. Participants expressed that music enables them to feel calmer and more positive in critical situations. They also feel that the music enhances intimacy between them and their loved ones as music presents the emotions of the patient. The family could also bring in their own imagination to interpret what the music represents.

Theme	Description	Examples
Evoking positive emotions	Pleasantness in music can evoke the feeling of connectedness.	P4: "I feel connected when the music is positive and clear."
	Tenderness in the music can help calm the family.	P3: "I like the music, because of the slow tempo, which is good for relaxing."
	Intimacy can be evoked from music with more details and variations.	P4: "The feeling of intimacy evoked by music B was stronger than A, because music A was calm and plain, while music B has more elements with buzzing and details."
Presenting the patient	Continuous stream of music enables people to feel the presence of their loved one.	P2: "The continuous stream of music is like a representative of them, enabling me to feel them."
	Using music similar to heartbeats to represent the patient can evoke anxiety.	P1: "I worried if the music was going to slow down or go faster. [...] Using tempo to present the heartbeat felt too literal."
	People may find it meaningful when the music is more related to emotions and activities.	P1: "It feels meaningful if it is more related to emotions and not as a way to monitor." P4: "The patient in music B might be conscious. They are active and moving around, and awake, while [the patient in] music A feels like sleeping."
Meaning of the music	People worry about misinterpreting the music when the music presents crucial information.	P2: "I want to know what the music and rhythm actually mean. [...] I want to know what to expect and what means 'bad'. P3: "I might misinterpret the music. [...] I am worried that if the heartbeat slows down, the music would change." P6: "When a new sound appears I wonder what it means."

Table 2. Results of the first round of user interviews.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we explored the role of music in the ICU and its potential for reutilizing patient data in a way that corresponds to the psychological and emotional needs of ICU users. We studied patient data and found ways to represent it musically. Our explorations provided evidence that music has the power to represent changes in patient vitals when used as an update tool for nurses replacing yellow non-actionable alarms and emotionally regulate families’ anxieties when used a messaging tool. Our prototypes prioritized possibilities for sonification and did not tackle actual system design, which will be the priority for the next design iteration for CareTunes in the near future.

Furthermore, we did not study the effect of musical data representation on patients. Live music has shown to be effective in reduction of pain. Patients own musical data may have a positive effect on regulation heart rate and variations. Following studies will look into physiological effect of music on patients, what music could mean to different types of patients (neonates, children, and adults) and how individual music preferences can be dealt with. Music as a therapeutic tool will be so investigated. In addition, this is an explorative study in sonification and its clinical relevance must be tested in randomized controlled trials.

Theme	Description	Examples
Evoking positive emotions	The music is able to help the family stay calm.	P2: "It sounds calm. [...] He is not recovering, but i wouldn't feel very sad because the emotion can be controlled. [...] I feel assured because the chords are brighter. [...] I feel calm because the pace is slow and not anxious. [...] I could face it and accept it."
Presenting the patient	Families may picture the patients differently when listening to their music.	P1: "It feels like she is peacefully lying on a field of grass." P2: "It feels like he is recovering, and not so lonely and bored."
Meaning of the music	People become less worried about their interpretation when the music does not present crucial information.	P1: "The atmosphere is good, and I would not analyze the music carefully. I would not worry if anything bad happens."
Data for generating the music	Families find the music meaningful when it is generated from brain waves.	P1: "Anything the person generates is 'real'. Heart represents the sign of life, but brain waves bring in emotions. [...] The brain-waves-generated music makes me assured."
Music composition	The multiple music tracks with different characteristics help construct multidimensional scenes or stories.	P1: "I thought of the meadow because of the light and crisp sounds. [...] The foreground is lively with flowers and birds, and the background is steady. [...] There are also big waves which feel like the wind." P2: "The [bell] sounds are like external stimulations [...] and the background sounds describe his feelings."

Table 3. Results of the second round of user interviews.

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